
Zero-touch Cross-Domain Orchestration in the 6G Compute Continuum: A Framework Evaluation in Real-Life Scenarios

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ABSTRACT The distribution of services across heterogeneous edge and cloud infrastructures in Beyond 5G (B5G) and Sixth-Generation (6G) networks increases operational complexity, while existing Management and Orchestration (MANO) solutions remain single-domain and lack unified telemetry or autonomous cross-domain decision mechanisms. Prior work proposes cross-domain orchestration concepts, but most validations rely on simulation and overlook interoperability issues, non-stationary latency, and inconsistent Key Performance Indicator (KPI) models in real Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) deployments. This paper introduces a modular, technology-agnostic Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) framework that provides unified NFVI abstraction and a multi-criteria decision engine that jointly considers latency, compute load, and energy consumption for autonomous service placement, scaling, and dynamic resource provisioning. Evaluation in a real-world deployment across geographically distributed testbeds demonstrates that our ZSM framework mitigates latency spikes by up to 96%, reduces overloaded-node latency by 36%, and maintains stable performance under variable load. These results confirm the practicality and effectiveness of zero-touch, multi-domain orchestration for future 6G compute-continuum environments.

INDEX TERMS 6G, Autonomous Network Management, Compute Continuum, Cross-domain Orchestration, Edge Computing, Network Softwarization, Technology-agnostic, Zero-touch Management

I. INTRODUCTION

Sixth-Generation (6G) networks aim to integrate heterogeneous computing and communication resources into a distributed continuum spanning the Radio Access Network (RAN), edge platforms, and cloud infrastructures [1], as illustrated in Figure 1. This evolution requires management systems capable of coordinating diverse administrative and technological domains, which expose different resource models, telemetry formats, and Life Cycle Management (LCM) procedures [2], [3]. While Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) provide programmability for flexible service deployment, they also increase operational complexity due to the scale, distribution, and dynamism of modern services [4]–[6]. This complexity is driven by the exponential growth in connected User Equipment (UE), user mobility, and distributed de-

ployments across operators and regions, necessitating more flexible and responsive orchestration capabilities [7].

For example, a teleoperated vehicle depends on ultra-reliable, low-latency connectivity for remote control and safety. As shown in Figure 1, when crossing technological or administrative boundaries (e.g., between edge sites), an autonomous management system must guarantee uninterrupted service. Acting as an orchestrator, it dynamically provisions edge resources and proactively migrates service functions to nodes in the target domain, thereby maintaining stringent Quality of Service (QoS). Achieving such continuity demands highly autonomous orchestration that integrates seamlessly with heterogeneous Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) [8].

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) proposes the Zero-touch Network and Service

FIGURE 1. Cross-domain integrated orchestration across heterogeneous administrative and technological domains through the compute continuum.

Management (ZSM) paradigm to address these challenges through intent-driven, closed-loop automation [4], [5], [9], [10]. However, the ZSM reference architecture does not define concrete mechanisms for harmonizing heterogeneous NFVI, unifying domain-specific telemetry, or coordinating decisions across domains with incompatible abstractions. Existing research on cross-domain orchestration often relies on simulation or emulation and typically evaluates simplified deployments or single-testbed setups [8], [11]–[13]. As a result, these studies overlook interoperability challenges, non-stationary latency behavior, workload variability, and inconsistent Key Performance Indicator (KPI) semantics that arise in real operational environments.

This work addresses these gaps by designing a modular and technology-agnostic ZSM framework that enables autonomous cross-domain orchestration across heterogeneous NFVI. The framework includes a distributed abstraction layer that standardizes domain interactions and normalizes diverse telemetry sources. This design eliminates operational silos, simplifies telemetry analytics, and supports autonomous orchestration with minimal human intervention. A multi-criteria decision engine evaluates latency, compute load, and energy consumption to autonomously optimize service placement and scaling in real time. The architecture aligns with ETSI ZSM and Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) principles while remaining compatible with existing SDN, NFV, and Kubernetes (K8s)-based environments.

This work addresses key limitations in the state of the art by the following contributions:

- 1) A modular and technology-agnostic ZSM framework that introduces the Domain Control Wrapper for harmonizing diverse monitoring data formats and standardizing lifecycle management interfaces, effectively enabling seamless interoperability in cross-domain resource coordination. This contribution advances be-

yond SotA approaches focused on theoretical ZSM foundations by enabling the coherent integration of heterogeneous NFVI domains and their unified, autonomous orchestration without requiring infrastructure modifications.

- 2) A performance and energy-aware, multi-criteria decision engine that elevates sustainability to a primary orchestration goal, supported by an empirical analysis of the correlation between latency and power consumption. This advances beyond traditional latency-centric approaches by enabling autonomous, energy-efficient resource orchestration operations.
- 3) A rigorous real-world validation across three geographically distributed testbeds in Belgium, Italy, and Romania. Unlike the prevalent simulation-based studies in the state of the art, this work demonstrates the feasibility and robustness of zero-touch cross-domain orchestration under live network conditions and distinct administrative domains.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the state of the art. Section III introduces key technological enablers for ZSM. Section IV details our proposed framework, and Section V describes its implementation. Section VI presents the validation results, which are then discussed in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORKS

The literature reflects a growing interest in enabling dynamic, data-driven cross-domain orchestration [8], [18], [21]. Key research themes include developing modular, vendor-agnostic frameworks [11], integrating diverse data sources for enhanced observability [19], and optimizing resource allocation in edge and cloud-native environments [12]. The following subsections review State of the Art (SotA) approaches in these areas, providing a foundation for understanding the contributions and context of our work.

A. STATE OF THE ART REVIEW

Recent research has made important strides in orchestration and service placement across emerging network architectures, increasingly focusing on higher degrees of automation and intelligence aligned with ZSM principles, as summarized in Table 1.

Inspired by the ETSI ZSM reference architecture, Barrachina-Muñoz et al. [18] introduce a modular and distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven architecture. This framework presents a slicing model in which an E2E umbrella slice coordinates multiple specialized supporting slices, each operating within a distinct management domain. The ZSM framework includes four main components monitoring systems, analytical engines, decision engines, and actuators which enable efficient orchestration of network slices. The framework leverages AI to enhance resource allocation, using Federated Learning (FL) to predict Central Processing Unit (CPU) usage and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)

TABLE 1. Overview of Standards and Related Works on ZSM.

Category	Year	Ref.	Contribution
Standards and Specifications	2020–2023	[4], [5], [10], [14]	ETSI GS ZSM defines the reference architecture, closed-loop automation, and intent-based management for cross-domain orchestration and autonomous operation.
	2024	[9]	ETSI GS ENI specifies adaptive, policy-driven decision loops and context-aware management aligned with ZSM.
	2024	[15]	3GPP TS 22.186 sets service requirements for advanced Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) in Fifth-Generation (5G), including platooning, remote driving, and extended sensors.
Survey Review	2022	[7]	Survey of zero-touch management for 5G/6G, covering automation taxonomy, standards, enabling technologies, and open challenges.
	2022	[2]	Review of zero-touch management for 5G and beyond, addressing architecture, lifecycle management, standards, and research gaps.
Studies on Applied ZSM and Cross-Domain Orchestration	2023	[16]	ZSM-based local 5G management using ML for traffic prediction, monitoring, and automated operations.
	2023	[17]	Cloud-native onboarding of service artefacts across domains, enabling synchronized vertical service management per ETSI ZSM.
	2024	[18]	Zero-touch slicing in Beyond 5G (B5G)/6G, validated with Vulnerable Road User (VRU) streaming and AI-driven optimization in a 5G testbed.
	2024	[19]	ZSM framework using crowdsourced UE metrics to improve automation and detect coverage, mobility, and interference issues.
	2024	[20]	Microservices-based NFV orchestration for 6G using Double Deep Q Learning (DDQL)/Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) to optimize resources and QoS.
	2024	[21]	ML-based ZSM orchestration with Deep Q Learning (DQL), optimizing resource allocation and service performance.
	2022	[11]	Resource orchestration for End-to-End (E2E) 5G Network Slicing (NS), automating high-performance management validated with ETSI ZSM use cases.
	2024	[12]	AI/ML-enabled relocation of automotive services across domains, aligned with ETSI ZSM.
	2024	[13]	Blueprint for integrating MANO-as-a-service (MANOaaS)/heterogeneous MANO-as-a-service (H-MANOaaS) into ETSI ZSM, validated via Proof-of-Concept (PoC) deployment.
	2024	[8]	Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based service placement across the compute continuum in 6G, optimizing latency and resource use.

to optimize RAN bandwidth in a radio resource management scenario. In that scenario, DRL is used for Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) optimization to comply with Service-Level Agreements (SLAs). However, reliance on specialized, pre-defined models for forecasting and optimization may limit adaptability to unforeseen network conditions or novel use cases not covered by the training data.

Tarrías et al. explore the concept of ZSM in cellular networks [19] by proposing a framework that integrates crowdsourced metrics from UEs. These metrics, termed Next-Generation Crowdsourcing Metrics (gCMs), combine lower-layer data such as radio performance indicators like Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) and Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ) with application-level data to provide a comprehensive view of network performance and Quality of Experience (QoE). The study analyzes both mobile and stationary data from real users, which are then processed using Machine Learning (ML) techniques to enhance network management capabilities, including detecting coverage holes, mobility issues, and interference problems. The authors envision this approach within the OpenRAN

initiative¹, where UE-based metrics are processed by a Radio Application (rApp) on the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) to optimize RAN functions. However, the paper acknowledges that significant challenges related to data heterogeneity, standardization, and full OpenRAN integration remain unresolved.

Aiming to improve performance and resource efficiency, Kopp and Melo [21] propose an ML-based service orchestration approach for Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) environments that leverages SDN. Their method uses five Perspective Indicators (Availability, Demand, Cost, Utility, and Perturbation) and a DQL agent to dynamically adjust service instances, such as caching for video distribution, based on monitored data. Their tool is designed to enable a single instance to manage multiple nodes by sharing resources and operational cycles, reducing per-node costs and enabling parallel operations for horizontal scalability. While the approach shows promise for optimizing resource allocation in simulated environments, its reliance on a complex DQL model raises challenges regarding interpretability

¹OpenRAN Project: <https://telecominfraproject.com/openran/>

TABLE 2. Comparison of contributions and limitations for the proposed ZSM framework and representative related works.

Contribution	This Work	Baba et al. [11]	Baranda et al. [12]	Correa et al. [13]	Ocampo et al. [8]
Modular, technology-agnostic ZSM framework	Modular, technology-agnostic architecture enabling cross-domain orchestration via Domain Control Wrapper and ETSI ZSM Integration Fabric.	E2E orchestration for multi-domain 5G (RAN/Transport Network (TN)/Core Network (CN)) using ETSI ZSM; no federation.	Automotive service relocation across two domains with ETSI ZSM and Open Source Management and Orchestration (MANO); limited to vehicular mobility.	Instantiation of H-MANOaaS within ZSM, enabling per-slice MANO; single-site PoC, no runtime orchestration.	RL-based service placement with real Fourth-Generation (4G)/5G traces; no live MANO/ZSM integration.
Performance-driven and Energy-Aware Multi-Criteria decision-making Orchestration	Power as first-class KPI; demonstrated energy-latency trade-off. Extensible, unit-agnostic KPI sets; adaptive orchestration logic.	No energy-awareness; KPIs limited to throughput/latency. Policy-based closed-loop automation with SLA and performance metrics.	No energy-awareness; optimization for latency and continuity only. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)-driven mobility prediction and edge PoP selection.	Deployment time measured; no operational KPIs or runtime optimization.	Energy optimization deferred; multi-objective RL rewards (latency, bandwidth, fairness).
Real-world validation	Three heterogeneous testbeds across Belgium, Italy, and Romania with live KPI collection and orchestration.	Experimental 5G setup with emulated RAN, real SDN transport and CN; single-operator scope.	Vehicular mobility simulation (SUMO) and demo in 5G Lab; limited to two domains and one vertical.	Validation on real servers with heterogeneous MANO; single site, deployment-time metrics only.	Real operator traces; simulation only, no live testbed.

and transparency. Furthermore, validation is confined to simulations, leaving performance and scalability in large-scale, real-world deployments untested.

In the related field of edge computing, Baranda et al. [12] propose a solution for proactive network service relocation for Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM) applications in automotive use cases across multiple distributed administrative domains. Their cloud-native approach integrates ETSI NFV and ZSM standards, using AI/ML to predict vehicle trajectories and optimize service placement at the most suitable edge Point of Presence (PoP). The PoPs are integrated into the ZSM framework via the Integration Fabric, as specified in ETSI ZSM guidelines, to trigger LCM operations. While innovative, the solution still faces significant challenges, such as scalability under high vehicle density and the complexity of cross-domain communication in real-world deployments.

Correa et al. [13] introduce the concept of heterogeneous MANOaaS, enabling the instantiation of diverse MANO frameworks per slice using a Data Center Virtualization Manager. Ocampo et al. [8] propose a reinforcement learning-based service placement strategy across the compute continuum, leveraging real 4G/5G network traces and multi-objective reward functions to optimize latency, cost, and bandwidth across different NFVIs. Baba et al. [11] present an end-to-end orchestration architecture spanning RAN, transport, and core technological domains, integrating closed-loop automation and standard Application Programmable Interfaces (APIs) to manage slice lifecycles. Baranda et al. [12] demonstrate a proactive relocation mechanism for vehicular services across administrative management domains, combining AI/ML mobility prediction with cross-domain orchestration to ensure service continuity in edge scenarios.

While the related works reviewed in this section address important aspects of orchestration, several operational gaps remain:

- **Validation in Real-World Infrastructures:** Many existing approaches rely on simulations or narrow vertical scenarios and therefore lack validation in realistic setups. We address this gap by validating the full ZSM framework across three geographically distributed testbeds in Belgium, Italy, and Romania.
- **Energy-aware Decision-making:** Prior studies rarely treat energy consumption as a primary KPI, meaning sustainability is often excluded from their decision process. We incorporate power consumption as one of the core metrics and study the strong correlation between QoS metrics such as E2E latency and the power consumption to drive energy-aware orchestration.
- **Interoperability across Heterogeneous NFVI:** Interoperability remains limited, as many solutions depend on vendor-specific mechanisms that hinder coordination. We overcome this through the Domain Control Wrapper, which harmonizes data interaction across domains and supports multi-criteria decision-making approaches.

B. DELTA ANALYSIS

The preceding analysis of the SotA reveals critical gaps in interoperability, sustainability, and real-world validation. The following subsections are therefore structured around our core contributions, demonstrating how our framework is architected to overcome these specific limitations and move beyond the theoretical and simulated approaches prevalent in the literature.

1) Modular and Technology-Agnostic ZSM Framework

A primary challenge identified in existing research is the prevalence of technology-specific solutions tied to particular domains, which lack true vendor-agnostic interoperability. To counter this, our first contribution is a modular, technology-agnostic ZSM framework with a dedicated abstraction layer, as detailed in Section IV. This design enables seamless cross-domain orchestration across heterogeneous NFVIs. Unlike approaches confined to a single vertical or lacking runtime orchestration capabilities, as noted in Table 2, our ZSM framework supports dynamic onboarding and offboarding of diverse infrastructures. This agnostic design breaks down silos often found in traditional network setups, enabling integrated E2E services without being constrained by proprietary hardware or software stacks. Consequently, it directly addresses the problem of vendor lock-in.

2) Heterogeneous Analytics for Multi-Criteria Orchestration

The core innovation of the framework lies in its ability to process diverse data types through unified, technology-agnostic analytics, streamlining orchestration with minimal human intervention. Prior works have often focused narrowly on performance metrics such as latency, while treating sustainability as secondary and leaving energy optimization for future exploration [8]. In contrast, our framework elevates power consumption to a first-class KPI, alongside latency and resource utilization, to enable sustainable and cost-effective resource management. A multi-criteria decision engine evaluates these dimensions simultaneously, autonomously managing service placement and scaling in near-real time. By actively addressing the energy-latency trade-off, the framework delivers actionable, energy-aware solutions that balance conflicting objectives, which is an essential yet frequently overlooked requirement for 6G networks.

3) Real-World Validation and Dynamic Orchestration

A significant limitation of the SotA is its reliance on simulated environments or single-operator testbeds, which leaves the performance and scalability of many solutions untested under realistic conditions. As shown in Table 2, our work moves beyond simulation by validating our interoperable solution through live service migration and scaling across three geographically distributed, heterogeneous testbeds. By orchestrating mission-critical vehicular services and other applications simultaneously across NFVI-based management domains, each operating within a distinct technological domain (e.g., edge or cloud), we demonstrate the ability of the ZSM framework to perform dynamic, cross-domain resource management. This addresses the inherent complexity of coordinating multiple disparate NFVI environments. For instance, our results show that the orchestrator successfully maintains a low E2E latency of approximately 16 ms in a

5G environment by migrating services under load, while simultaneously managing resources in other management domains with different KPI priorities.

III. ZSM ENABLERS

This section presents the essential enablers required for a comprehensive understanding of the ZSM paradigm. These enablers play a pivotal role in laying the groundwork for realizing the ZSM framework and achieving its ambitious goals.

A. NETWORK PROGRAMMABILITY

The evolution of network technology is characterized by a shift toward softwarization, which leverages virtualization and programmability to redefine network and service architectures [3]. SDN facilitates the management of network services by abstracting underlying hardware functionalities. Its architecture separates the control plane, which contains the network logic, from the data plane, which handles packet forwarding. This separation allows network applications to interact with devices in the data plane, exposing programmable functionalities to retrieve network status information or apply configurations in an abstract form [22].

SDN enables architectural and cost optimization when combined with technologies such as NFV, which virtualizes network functions on standard hardware through a software-driven model for designing, deploying, and managing services. Together, they facilitate abstraction and disaggregation of service functions, providing the foundation for flexible and scalable MANO solutions. SDN and NFV are indispensable enablers of the ZSM paradigm, which pursues a high degree of automation. To achieve this, MANO governs infrastructure complexity by automating the lifecycle of virtualized services and executing the decisions made within the ZSM architecture.

B. MANAGEMENT AND ORCHESTRATION

High levels of automation in ZSM are achieved through closed-loop control, which follows the continuous cycle of monitoring, analysis, decision-making, and execution defined by the Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute-Knowledge (MAPE-K) model [5], [23]. Monitoring collects critical information on service status and the availability and performance of computing and networking resources. Telemetry mechanisms provide real-time visibility into these conditions, forming the basis for informed orchestration decisions.

Orchestration in heterogeneous 6G environments spanning technological and management domains across the compute continuum requires rapid adaptation of service placement and normalization of telemetry. This agility is enabled by containerization, which packages applications into lightweight, portable units. Platforms such as Kubernetes² provide declarative APIs and automation to manage

²Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io/>

containers at scale, supporting rapid deployment and LCM in dynamic 6G scenarios.

To enable autonomous and intelligent network management, the ETSI ZSM specifications advocate the use of AI/ML techniques to enhance orchestration processes such as decision-making [5]. Although this paper outlines several potential applications of AI/ML in network management, our primary emphasis is on the architectural framework that supports automation and orchestration, rather than on the design of specific AI/ML models.

Established NFV MANO platforms such as ETSI Open Source Management and Orchestration (OSM)³ and Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP)⁴ offer standardized descriptors and LCM for Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs), but their models remain tailored to centralized, VM-centric telco cloud environments. These limitations indicate that future orchestration must evolve toward intent-based approaches, where high-level service objectives are expressed as intents and automatically translated into enforceable policies and configurations [10].

C. INTENT-BASED NETWORKING

Intent-Based Networking (IBN) transforms network and service management by translating high-level goals into automated actions, where an intent declaratively defines the desired outcome and focuses on what should be achieved rather than how it should be implemented [6], [10], [24]. For example, a high-level intent can be: “Ensure E2E latency below 100 ms”. The network and service management system then automatically updates configurations to meet the stated QoS requirements. An intent can be broken down into smaller, more specific sub-intents for each relevant management domain, each operating within a specific technological context (e.g., RAN, edge, and core).

According to the ETSI IBN specifications, three key components work together to translate business objectives into automated network actions [10]: 1) **intent owners**, who define high-level goals; 2) the **Intent Management Entity (IME)**, which processes and coordinates intents; and 3) **intent handlers**, which execute intents within their respective domains. The IME plays a key role in enabling cross-domain orchestration in the ZSM reference architecture [4], and it is fundamental for achieving the self-managing capabilities that define the ZSM paradigm [25].

IV. ZSM FRAMEWORK ARCHITECTURE

This section explains how the ZSM paradigm turns high-level capabilities such as automation, programmability, and orchestration into an operational architecture. ZSM envisions autonomous, policy-driven lifecycle operations in which networks and services configure, optimize, and adapt with minimal human intervention. These capabilities are realized through concrete architectural components, interfaces, and

FIGURE 2. ETSI reference ZSM architecture [4].

control loops that enable scalable and autonomous service and resource management.

A. STANDARDIZED REFERENCE ZSM ARCHITECTURE

In 2017, the ETSI established the ZSM Industry Specification Group (ISG) to lead standardization efforts in designing a framework for network automation based on ZSM principles [4]. The ETSI reference ZSM framework architecture is designed to support comprehensive E2E service management across a wide range of technological and administrative domains [4]. A central goal of this framework is to automate these management processes [5], as shown in Figure 2. To support interoperability and platform independence, service models are intentionally decoupled from their underlying software implementations.

Decoupling service models from their implementations increases flexibility but challenges reliability, as current frameworks struggle with disruption detection in dynamic topologies and heterogeneous data processing [5], [9]. The ZSM framework addresses this through closed-loop automation that monitors network and service states, detects anomalies, and triggers self-healing. Autonomous and reliable management in B5G/6G networks further requires standardized analytics interfaces to integrate monitoring data from diverse sources. Within ZSM, data normalization ensures consistent interpretation, enabling interoperability and automated decision-making during orchestration [4], [23].

³ETSI OSM: <https://osm.etsi.org/docs/user-guide/latest/>

⁴ONAP: <https://www.onap.org/architecture>

Figure 2 illustrates how the ETSI reference ZSM architecture defines a *Management Domain* as a distinct area of responsibility within the network, determined by factors such as technology, geographic scope, or administrative control [4], [7]. Within each management domain, advanced MANO operations are structured into specific functional blocks that support modular and autonomous network and service management.

- *Management Functions*: to automate the management and orchestration of network and service resources within a domain supporting tasks such as monitoring and fault management.
- *Data Services*: to enable authorized, cross-domain data handling through persistent storage and controlled sharing among management entities.
- *Domain Integration Fabric*: to expose and control the management services accessible internally and by other domains.

The *Management Functions* encompass a set of capabilities for achieving intelligent, automated service management. These include:

- E2E Orchestration coordinates services across domains through automated provisioning and LCM, ensuring consistent delivery.
- E2E Intelligence applies AI/ML to enable autonomous decisions for resource optimization and anomaly detection.
- E2E Analytics processes performance metrics from monitoring, enabling proactive adaptation to dynamic conditions.
- E2E Data Collection aggregates and normalizes telemetry and events from diverse segments, providing unified input for analytics and orchestration.

Although functions within each management domain are modular, they interact with other domains through a Cross-domain Integration Fabric, enabling E2E services across administrative and technological boundaries [4]. In the ZSM framework, these functions operate in closed-loop cycles, allowing MANO to collect data and perform near real-time adjustments based on analytics. As shown in Figure 3, two IMEs are positioned at different levels: one near intent owners, where high-level requirements are defined, and the other integrated with orchestration processes across the domain fabric and the NFVI of the managed domain.

Figure 3 shows the conceptual design of the ZSM framework, where the enablers from Section III converge into an integrated architecture. Built on programmable, virtualized infrastructure (NFV) and governed by MANO functions, the framework executes multi-criteria decisions within a closed-loop control. High-level goals are translated into automated actions through IBN, while AI/ML provides intelligence for intent translation, analytics, and decision-making. A unifying fabric enables cross-domain integration, ensuring seamless

FIGURE 3. The ZSM framework architecture, representing key technological enablers for autonomous orchestration.

orchestration across diverse management domains, including heterogeneous NFVIs.

The ZSM framework in Figure 3 is designed with modular Intelligence interfaces that can support advanced AI and ML models for tasks such as intent translation, decision-making and prediction. We opt for a simpler approach to test the robustness of autonomous orchestration operations. The scope of this paper therefore focuses on validating the architectural framework itself, including data normalization and decision execution across heterogeneous domains. The integration of advanced AI models is outside the scope of this study, although the architecture is explicitly designed to support their future adoption for predictive and proactive orchestration.

For practical deployment in 5G and future networks, the ZSM architecture can align with 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standards. It extends automation across the compute continuum, interfacing with the 3GPP ecosystem by consuming analytics from functions such as Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) and issuing control commands to domain-specific controllers. Instead of interacting directly with low-level MANO components, the framework delegates enforcement to specialized entities like the RIC in the RAN, TN Controllers, or CN management functions. To further simplify integration and monitoring, the framework can leverage network exposure interfaces, such as CAMARA APIs⁵, to abstract the underlying complexity of these heterogeneous infrastructures. This positions the framework as a unified E2E orchestrator for complex services across heterogeneous NFVIs, a key enabler for advanced 6G use cases.

⁵CAMARA Project: <https://camaraproject.org/>

FIGURE 4. Our ZSM Framework Architecture

In parallel, the ETSI ENI architecture [9] extends the ZSM paradigm with adaptive, policy-driven decision loops and context-aware management. ENI adds a cognitive layer that learns from environmental and service conditions, translating high-level policies into orchestration actions. Together, ZSM and ENI form complementary foundations: ZSM delivers intent-driven automation across domains, while ENI strengthens adaptability and resilience through experiential intelligence.

B. OUR ZSM ARCHITECTURE

Building on the ETSI ZSM and ENI reference architectures [4], [9], this section transitions from the standardized model to our concrete architectural design. While the ETSI standards provide a foundational blueprint for cross-domain orchestration, concrete implementation details for data harmonization and intent translation are unspecified. This abstraction presents a significant practical challenge for achieving true interoperability. Our architecture addresses this challenge by introducing a concrete realization of the integration fabric logic, bridging the gap between the theoretical ZSM model and a deployable, operational framework.

To the best of our knowledge, while most orchestration solutions are tailored to specific technological domains, our framework is engineered as a comprehensive ZSM solution that provides unified cross-domain orchestration for heterogeneous environments. Our ZSM framework is built on a modular architecture that promotes interoperability by enabling automated onboarding of new management domains spanning different edge/cloud environments. At its core is a multi-criteria decision-making engine that balances trade-offs among network performance, computing load, and energy consumption across management domains, each with its

own NFVI. The following components, shown in Figure 4, are integrated to deliver these autonomous orchestration capabilities:

- **ZSM Monitoring:** is a component of the *Domain Data Collection* function within the *E2E Analytics* subsystem, responsible for extracting and distributing performance metrics (e.g., compute, network, energy) and NFVI attributes (e.g., identity, location, deployment details) from resources within a management domain. Acting as a data source, it forwards this information to other ZSM components, such as Subscribers, via publish/subscribe mechanisms. By providing real-time and historical data, ZSM monitoring supports service health assessment, anomaly detection, and resource optimization. Closely integrated with the Domain Integration Fabric, the Subscribers are responsible for receiving and consolidating telemetry published by distributed Publishers across multiple management domains, organizing incoming data into structured datasets that feed near-real-time analytics and orchestration processes.
- **ZSM Orchestrator:** incorporates functional characteristics that correspond to the *E2E Orchestration* and *E2E Intelligence* components identified in the reference ZSM architecture. The ZSM Orchestrator acts as the central decision-making engine, responsible for determining how to best allocate and manage resources to meet dynamic service requirements. It processes a wide array of data, including near-real-time performance metrics (e.g., E2E latency, CPU load, power consumption), NFVI attributes (e.g., descriptions of capabilities and management domain-specific priorities for KPI-driven decision-making), and external contextual information. These external contextual data sources refer to telemetry not originating from the network infrastructure itself (e.g., environmental sensors, vertical-specific analytics) but which can be correlated with internal KPIs to influence orchestration decisions. In dynamic 5G/6G environments, particularly for mission-critical applications like connected vehicles, decisions must be made in near-real-time to ensure service continuity and optimal performance. Based on this data, the orchestrator makes critical decisions, such as scaling (adjusting resources up or down) and service placement (where to deploy or redeploy services to maintain QoS). These decisions are then communicated as deployment strategies to the ZSM Control component.
- **ZSM Control:** is responsible for executing the decisions made by the ZSM Orchestrator, which are translated into deployment actions such as instantiating new services, scaling services or resources up or down, migrating services between nodes, or terminating existing services. The ZSM Framework uses the IBN principle internally to transmit decisions as sub-intents from the ZSM Orchestrator to Deployer components via the *Domain Control Wrapper*. Task fulfillment is

TABLE 3. Application of ZSM architectural references and their analogies with the ZSM Framework PoC.

ZSM Framework PoC	ZSM Architecture Reference	ENI Architecture Component
ZSM Monitoring	E2E Data Collection/E2E Analytics	Context Awareness/Knowledge Management
ZSM Orchestration Functions	E2E Orchestration/E2E Intelligence	ENI System
ZSM Control	Intent Management Entity/Domain Orchestration	API Translation in API Broker (optional)
Domain Control Wrapper	Cross-domain integration fabric	Input/Output normalization and denormalization
Orchestration Database Subsystem	Data Services	N/A
Management Closed-loop Control	Management Functions Closed-loop	E2E Closed Control Loops

checked periodically to ensure that actions are completed successfully. For example, if a service fails to instantiate, the Deployers send a request to re-execute the action. Conversely, if a task is still initializing, no further actions are taken to prevent overloading the orchestration queue and increasing lag. This self-diagnosis and self-healing mechanism is crucial for maintaining the stability and reliability of the orchestration process.

- Domain Control Wrapper:** acts as an abstraction layer that facilitates communication and control between different management domains in ZSM, as depicted in Table 3. As a component of the *Domain Integration Fabric*, it actively handles interactions between NFVIs, ZSM deployers, and ZSM orchestrators, including the exchange of information related to authentication, metrics, and service management actions such as instantiation, scaling (up/down), termination, and migration of services.
- Orchestration database subsystem:** Collected metrics are subsequently stored and managed by the orchestration database subsystem, deployed within the central management domain in accordance with the *E2E Data Collection* component from the ETSI ZSM architecture reference. This subsystem ensures data persistence and supports critical uses such as retrospective analysis, system auditing, and AI/ML model training to enable intelligent orchestration.

In our ZSM framework, closed-loop control spans orchestration and NFVI components by continuously monitoring data and executing actions asynchronously. This is a core capability that supports the orchestration functions previously described. It allows the system to continuously sense, analyze, and respond to changes in the network with minimal latency, enabling high levels of automation and adaptability in dynamic environments.

V. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ZSM FRAMEWORK IN THE 6G COMPUTE-COMMUNICATION CONTINUUM

This section presents a detailed case study of our ZSM framework, demonstrating its practical application in addressing the core challenge of simplifying cross-domain orchestration across heterogeneous NFVI. Real-world validation is essential to assess the ability of the ZSM framework to overcome the complexity of processing diverse data types

FIGURE 5. Implementation details of the ZSM framework components, highlighting the specific technologies that realize the architecture described in this section.

and to provide a unified, technology-agnostic analysis that streamlines orchestration with minimal human intervention in a demanding environment. Specifically, we evaluate:

- 1) Autonomous decision-making within ZSM to optimize resource allocation and ensure seamless service delivery for mission-critical applications (e.g., automotive and connected mobility).
- 2) Cross-domain orchestration that manages multiple heterogeneous management domains simultaneously and dynamically allocates resources in edge computing environments, as illustrated in Figure 6.

A. TESTBED ENVIRONMENTS

Our validation is performed across a distributed compute continuum, composed of three distinct administrative domains with their own underlying NFVIs, as depicted in Figure 6. These technological infrastructures are used to demonstrate the ability of the ZSM framework to orchestrate multiple management domains simultaneously under dynamic conditions across different scenarios, as shown in Figure 7. The primary objective is to demonstrate that our ZSM framework can orchestrate these heterogeneous domains in parallel, each governed by its own policies, rather

FIGURE 6. Geographically distributed technological domains for the validation of the ZSM framework to integrate and orchestrate heterogeneous NFVIs.

than deploying a single service across all of them. It is also important to note that a single administrative domain, such as the Smart Highway (SHW) testbed, can itself contain a localized compute continuum of distributed resources (e.g., edge nodes), which the ZSM framework also manages.

The first is the **SHW testbed**⁶ located in Antwerp, Belgium, which serves as a platform for wireless networking research. The second is the **Infrastructure in Italy (NFVI-I)** situated in Turin, Italy, which provides seamless service management through a LCM platform deployed atop its infrastructure. The third is the **Infrastructure in Romania (NFVI-R)**, based in Iași, enabling deployment and validation of smart mobility use cases over hybrid 5G and Edge infrastructure.

The **SHW testbed** in Antwerp, Belgium, is a key platform for wireless networking research in the automotive sector, providing a realistic environment to validate vehicular applications. The testbed spans 4 km of the E13 highway and includes distributed edge computing nodes on seven Roadside Units (RSUs) and two On-board Units (OBUs) (see Figure 7). These nodes host vehicular services within K8s clusters. Our ZSM framework is implemented as a K8s-native application that extends the default orchestration logic. To achieve this, we override the standard K8s scheduler with a custom decision-making engine. This engine leverages Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) to make placement decisions, enabling fine-grained control over service deployment based on real-time telemetry and domain-specific policies, rather than relying on the default resource-based scheduling of K8s.

The **NFVI-I** located in Turin, Italy, relies on the Telecom Italia (TIM) 5G commercial network based on a 3GPP Rel-15 Non-Standalone Architecture (NSA) deployment, with

⁶Smart Highway testbed: <https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research-groups/idlab/infrastructure/smart-highway/>

FIGURE 7. The ZSM Framework Setup integrating the NFVI LCM platform in Italy and the SHW testbed in Belgium.

applications running on top of a virtualized infrastructure. Service provisioning is managed by an innovative E2E orchestration solution, enabling concurrent services to be easily instantiated and scaled in real time through its own LCM platform interface, while Resource orchestration is further enhanced by dynamic allocation and lifecycle management of compute, storage, and networking resources, ensuring optimal utilization and smooth integration across both virtualized and containerized workloads. This infrastructure provides four working nodes based on K8s, as depicted in Figure 7.

The **NFVI-R** based in Iași, Romania, hosts a 5G Lab datacenter that leverages a 5G Standalone (SA) local User Plane Function (UPF) unit, integrated within a private 5G CN deployed in Bucharest and connected to 5G radio cells. It also includes edge computing servers with GPUs for video analytics applications in the Smart Crowd Monitoring and Smart Traffic Management use cases of the TrialsNet project. User-plane traffic is routed through the local UPF, while video surveillance streams are processed directly at the edge servers. A E2E orchestration platform connects central cloud and edge facilities, enabling continuous monitoring and control of E2E latency data from edge-deployed applications.

Our ZSM framework is validated through two deployment modes: on-site orchestration in the NFVI-R and remote orchestration integrating NFVI-I and SHW as displayed in Figure 6. In the latter, orchestration elements located in Belgium manage both the SHW testbed and the NFVI-I. This validation relies on the ZSM Domain Control Wrapper, a modular interface that abstracts the implementation details of each management domain, including its underlying NFVI and technological scope (e.g., edge or cloud).

B. CROSS-DOMAIN ORCHESTRATION OF HETEROGENEOUS NFVI

The Domain Control Wrapper establishes seamless communication between the ZSM Orchestrator and external NFVI

environments, allowing MANO functions to operate across heterogeneous infrastructures without modifying the framework core at runtime. By abstracting domain-specific APIs and resource models, the Domain Control Wrapper enables the ZSM orchestrator to manage the E2E service lifecycle across the compute continuum. This design strengthens the capacity of the ZSM framework to mitigate vendor lock-in and ensures reliable management of complex, multi-domain network environments.

To support this flexible and interoperable integration across diverse NFVI-based management domains, the Domain Control Wrapper is composed of four specialized modules: 1) *Authentication Manager* handles authentication procedures to validate and maintain secure connections between the ZSM framework and external management domains; 2) *Endpoint Mapper* exposes performance metrics from managed domains and relays deployment instructions from the ZSM Orchestrator to the deployers; 3) *Metrics Formatter* converts telemetry data into the standardized format required by the ZSM Orchestrator for analytics; and 4) *Orchestrator Bridge* connects the Domain Control Wrapper with ZSM Orchestrator endpoints, enabling analytics and control exchange between managed domains and the E2E Management Service Domain.

As the orchestrator evolves into an autonomous intent owner, it is essential to position the IMEs where high-level intents can be translated into executable actions. In our implementation, the IME is integrated as a core sub-function of the **Domain Control Wrapper**, as shown in Figure 4. Abstract decisions from the ZSM Orchestrator are routed to the wrapper, where the IME refines them into domain-specific sub-intents before forwarding them to the ZSM Deployer. This placement within the abstraction layer ensures that high-level goals are consistently enforced as concrete tasks tailored to the underlying NFVI.

The ZSM components communicate via Zenoh⁷, a lightweight pub/sub system optimized for low-overhead data exchange. Zenoh supports both discoverable and pre-configured Internet Protocol (IP) communication; the discoverable mode allows components to initialize without manual IP configuration, simplifying deployment, avoiding disruptions from dynamic IP changes, and enabling seamless scaling as nodes or NFVIs join or leave the ZSM framework ecosystem. Message payloads are structured in a normalized format (Figure 9), allowing heterogeneous NFVIs to expose metrics consistently. This standardization ensures smooth integration across diverse environments and provides the foundation for unified data management in cross-domain orchestration.

C. DATA MANAGEMENT TO SUPPORT CROSS-DOMAIN ORCHESTRATION

Figure 8 depicts the primary datasets generated and consumed throughout the framework, detailing their origin

FIGURE 8. Data structures used in the ZSM Framework Data Management flow.

FIGURE 9. Example of a standardized message format for cross-domain data exchange in the ZSM Framework.

and propagation across the architectural components. These structured datasets underpin the decision-making and deployment processes, forming the informational substrate for cross-domain orchestration. The main types of datasets are categorized as follows:

- 1) **Metrics:** refer to measurements collected from the infrastructure during operation, such as CPU usage, E2E latency, and power consumption, as shown in Figure 9. These are generated by publishers in ZSM Monitoring and encoded in a common structure containing fields such as origin, IP, metric type, and values, facilitating consistent processing across heterogeneous infrastructures.
- 2) **Decision Datasets:** contain the outputs generated by the Decision Engine during orchestration processes. They encapsulate analyzed information used to trigger and explain management actions, reflecting the reasoning of the system based on policy rules or learned behavior.
- 3) **Setup Description:** encodes information about the underlying infrastructure configuration of the *Managed Domains*, such as resource descriptors and dynamic decision prioritization based on context-specific goals like E2E latency, performance, or energy usage, as shown in Figure 9.
- 4) **Deployment Actions:** represent the concrete outputs of the orchestration process, including deployment

⁷Zenoh: <https://zenoh.io/>

Algorithm 1 Heterogeneous Data Source Normalization

Require: Telemetry Topic T_{sub} via Zenoh Middleware**Ensure:** Normalized System State S

```
1: Initialize Subscriber on  $T_{sub}$ 
2: function ONRECEIVE(telemetry)      ▷ Event-driven Execution
3:    $payload \leftarrow \text{Decode}(telemetry)$ 
4:    $config \leftarrow \text{ExtractSetup}(payload)$ 
5:    $platform \leftarrow \text{GetOrRegister}(config)$ 
6:   for each  $m \in payload.metrics$  do
7:      $norm\_m \leftarrow \text{Normalize}(m, config)$ 
8:     Update  $platform.metricsList$  with  $norm\_m$ 
9:     PushToAPI( $norm\_m$ )      ▷ Sync with ZSM DB
10:  end for
11:  MAKEDECISION      ▷ Trigger Control Loop
12: end function
```

TABLE 4. Multi-criteria decision-making for multi-domain orchestration.

NFVI	Priorities set	Node	KPI ₁	KPI ₂	KPI _{n...}
Setup ₁	Latency, Power, CPU	Node ₁	Value	Value	Value
Setup ₁	Latency, Power, CPU	Node ₂	Value	Value	Value
Setup ₂	Power, Latency, CPU	Node ₁	Value	Value	Value
Setup ₂	Power, Latency, CPU	Node ₂	Value	Value	Value

Algorithm 2 MCDM with Priority-Ordered Multi-key Ranking Across Management Domains

Require: List of management domains D **Ensure:** Selected nodes and contexts for orchestration

```
1: for each domain  $p \in D$  do
2:   Retrieve priority vector  $\Pi_p$  (ordered KPIs)
3:   Retrieve candidate records  $M_p$  from domain  $p$ 
4:   for each candidate  $m \in M_p$  do
5:     Construct tuple  $\kappa(m)$  following order in  $\Pi_p$ 
6:   end for
7:   Rank candidates by multi-key  $\kappa(m)$ 
8:   if top priority in  $\Pi_p$  is latency then
9:     if candidate exceeds latency tolerance then
10:      Update  $p.selected \leftarrow m$ 
11:     else
12:       Keep current  $p.selected$ 
13:     end if
14:   else
15:     Update  $p.selected$  by multi-key ranking
16:   end if
17:   Publish  $(p.selected, context)$  asynchronously
18: end for
```

blueprints, configuration templates, or low-level resource allocation instructions. Within the ZSM Control, deployers and the IME execute these actions as sub-intents, interfacing with the Domain Control Wrapper to apply changes in the target environment.

Algorithm 3 Deployment Action Enforcement

Require: Optimal Target Node N , Service Intent S **Ensure:** Deployment Verification Status

```
1: Verify operational status of Target Node  $N$ 
2: if Node  $N$  is Busy or Initializing then
3:   Wait to prevent command queue overload
4: end if
5: Dispatch instantiation command for  $S$  via Domain Control Wrapper
6: while Timeout not reached do
7:   Poll lifecycle state of service on Node  $N$ 
8:   if Service State is Active then
9:     return Success
10:  end if
11:  Wait for polling interval
12: end while
13: Trigger Error Handling Routine
14: return Failure
```

D. MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING IN THE ORCHESTRATION DECISION ENGINE

Each dataset compiled within the ZSM framework carries predefined priorities reflecting the operational goals of its originating management domain. For instance, data from the SHW testbed may emphasize low latency for vehicular safety, while another domain may prioritize energy efficiency. As shown in Table 4, these priorities determine how records are organized in in-memory snapshot tables and directly shape orchestration decisions for each NFVI. The analytics process proceeds in two stages (Algorithm 1): the ZSM Monitor acquires and structures data by platform and category, after which the Decision Engine evaluates the datasets to define orchestration actions. Dedicated threads execute data processing asynchronously, enabling MCDM tailored to the distinct requirements of heterogeneous domains.

MCDM provides a systematic method to: 1) balance conflicting objectives such as latency and power consumption; 2) process heterogeneous data from diverse infrastructures asynchronously; and 3) unify decision-making, avoiding specialized per-domain engines and improving scalability. Unlike RL, fuzzy-logic systems, or evolutionary algorithms [26], which often require extensive training data, scenario-specific tuning, or high computational overhead, MCDM offers a lightweight, explainable mechanism for evaluating trade-offs among heterogeneous KPIs. This enables the engine to handle standardized datasets prioritized by KPI thresholds, as shown in Table 4. Its asynchronous design further enhances resilience by decoupling data ingestion from analysis, preventing system-wide bottlenecks [5], [10].

The implemented Algorithm 2 applies the MCDM principle in the decision engine using multi-key ranking where items are sorted by several attributes based on a defined ordered sequence of priorities. For each management domain

$p \in D$, a priority vector Π_p defines the order of selected KPIs such as latency, power, or CPU. Candidate records M_p are processed to construct tuples $\kappa(m)$ according to Π_p , which are then used to rank nodes. When latency is the top priority, $p.selected$ is updated only if a candidate exceeds the configured tolerance, avoiding unnecessary reselection; otherwise, $p.selected$ is set by multi-key ranking. The resulting decision, consisting of $p.selected$ and its context, is published asynchronously over the messaging fabric for downstream orchestration actions such as placement, scaling, or migration.

After selecting the target node (Algorithm 3), its availability is verified to ensure it is not busy or initializing. The service is then instantiated via the Domain Control Wrapper. The service state is monitored through polling; if activation occurs within the timeout, the deployment succeeds. Otherwise, an error is raised and the deployment is marked as failed for re-trial.

E. ZSM DEPLOYMENT VARIANTS USED IN VALIDATION SCENARIOS

To validate the proposed cross-domain orchestration model (Sections A and B), built on multi-criteria decision-making, the ZSM framework is deployed across **three** distinct edge environments. These environments reflect specific application requirements and orchestration priorities and are evaluated in **three** scenarios:

- 1) **Mission-Critical Vehicular Services (SHW-A):** Designed for high-mobility environments, this scenario targets E2E latency below 100 ms. Although low latency for critical vehicular applications is often cited in the single-digit millisecond range [15], the 100 ms threshold is adopted as a realistic upper bound for this testbed, which lacks 5G connectivity, making ultra-low latencies (e.g., 20-30 ms) impractical; this reflects the complexities of live, large-scale environments. This threshold is nevertheless adequate to ensure reliable, near-real-time communication for protecting vulnerable road users (VRUs), where resources are dynamically allocated within edge computing environments to satisfy performance requirements.
- 2) **Energy-Aware Resource Allocation (SHW-B):** manages services based on energy constraints expressed in high-level intents while maintaining acceptable E2E latency to optimize power efficiency for sustainable operations under light vehicular traffic.
- 3) **Smart Traffic Management (NFVI-I and NFVI-R):** This scenario leverages video analytics, such as object detection, to enhance the safety of VRUs. Both NFVI-I and NFVI-R aim to ensure stringent QoS. The geographically remote NFVI-I validates cross-domain orchestration and demonstrates the ability of the ZSM framework to manage heterogeneous sources. In contrast, NFVI-R offers an on-site configuration for autonomous, self-adaptable network setup, providing

FIGURE 10. GUI of the ZSM Framework deployed on the SHW testbed.

a complementary validation environment beyond the SHW testbed.

VI. RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results from deploying our ZSM framework across three heterogeneous, real-world testbeds. We analyze the ability of our ZSM framework to process diverse data types and provide a unified, technology-agnostic analysis of heterogeneous telemetry to streamline cross-domain orchestration and to discuss the practical insights gained from these experiments.

A. MULTI-DOMAIN ORCHESTRATION FLOW

The ZSM framework can simultaneously monitor multiple NFVIs within a single deployment. Our ZSM framework integrates a graphical user interface that displays near real-time insights into the orchestration process. As seen in Figure 10, it enables continuous monitoring of each edge computing node, including performance metrics, service states (such as instantiation, scaling, and termination), and the specific priorities assigned to each management domain. The ZSM framework aims to achieve optimal performance and resource utilization across heterogeneous NFVI-based management domains through the following orchestration flow:

- **Step 1: ZSM Monitoring & Data Processing.** The monitoring process is driven by ZSM Publisher modules, which collect performance metrics such as E2E latency, CPU load, and power consumption directly from the NFVIs. In parallel, they gather essential metadata, including the location of the NFVI, KPI priorities, and the identity of the associated ZSM Deployer. This

TABLE 5. Overview of the three validation experiments.

Experiment	Location	Objective	Measured KPIs
1. Cross-domain integrated orchestration	Belgium (Smart Highway) and Italy (NFVI-I)	Validate the ability of the ZSM framework to coordinate heterogeneous monitoring data and enforce policies across distinct NFVI domains with different KPI priorities.	E2E latency per domain, orchestration adaptability, trade-offs from network conditions.
2. On-site orchestration validation	Romania (NFVI-R)	Test the framework in a real 5G setup with edge orchestration, ensuring QoS for mission-critical video detection in smart traffic.	E2E latency under 5G, QoS stability, service resilience under load.
3. Energy-aware ZSM for sustainable solutions	Belgium (SHW facilities)	Assess how correlating performance with energy monitoring supports sustainable orchestration, leveraging a technological agnostic architectural design.	E2E latency, CPU usage, energy consumption, sustainability impact.

combined data is then received by ZSM Subscriber modules within the Integration Fabric, which continuously process and structure the datasets for the decision engine.

- Step 2: ZSM Orchestration & Decision-Making.** The ZSM Orchestrator uses the prepared datasets to make decisions. Its core decision engine concurrently evaluates the data from all monitored managed domains, applying MCDM analysis to satisfy the unique priorities of each NFVI. Once a decision is made, the orchestrator sends it to the designated ZSM Deployer for the respective NFVI.
- Step 3: ZSM Control & Enforcement.** The final step is handled by the ZSM Control components, specifically the ZSM Deployers. Upon receiving a decision, the ZSM Deployer executes the necessary action on its corresponding NFVI, such as service migration or resource scaling. The ZSM Deployers also perform local checks on service status to ensure correct operation and are responsible for triggering autonomous recovery actions in case of failure.

B. EVALUATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In support of this evaluation, three complementary experiments are conducted to validate the proposed ZSM framework across heterogeneous environments, as displayed in Table 5. The common goal is to demonstrate the flexibility, modularity, and network-agnostic design of the ZSM framework, showing that it is not tied exclusively to 5G but can adapt to the unique requirements of multiple NFVI-based management domains, such as prioritizing low latency, energy efficiency, or QoS, while remaining plug-and-play and adaptable to different infrastructures.

In this context, the decision-making engine applies a multi-criteria approach guided by the management domain-specific priorities of each infrastructure to select optimal deployments that reflect the best overall trade-off across all management domains. The ZSM Domain Control Wrapper is essential for normalizing and enhancing interoperability between the different management systems involved in the cross-domain orchestration. It serves as middleware that se-

FIGURE 11. KPIs performance during cross-domain orchestration.

cures authentication, maintains sessions with external NFVI-based management domains, and ensures uninterrupted, protected data exchange.

The following results are derived from live experiments on physical infrastructure rather than simulations. We subjected the testbeds to real-world stress conditions such as incrementally increasing concurrent data user traffic up to saturation points. In the Smart Highway testbed, specifically, load generation was driven by real-time vehicle counts from inductive loop sensors to emulate realistic traffic demand. Consequently, the parameters analyzed including latency variations and power spikes represent actual system behavior under stress.

TABLE 6. Country-level KPI summary followed by node-level breakdown.

Country	Node	KPI	Mean (95% CI)	Std	Count	
Belgium	All	CPU (%)	4.16 [4.14, 4.19]	0.88	4646	
		E2E Latency (ms)	102.64 [102.15, 103.12]	8.72	1235	
		Power (wt)	62.87 [62.07, 63.67]	27.74	4646	
Italy	All	CPU (u)	0.75 [0.72, 0.78]	0.83	3720	
		E2E Latency (ms)	93.28 [91.98, 94.58]	37.46	3199	
Belgium	SHW-1	CPU (%)	4.46 [4.43, 4.5]	0.5	809	
		E2E Latency (ms)	101.62 [100.22, 103.01]	9.38	177	
		Power (wt)	49.03 [48.92, 49.14]	1.59	809	
	SHW-2	CPU (%)	4.12 [4.1, 4.15]	0.33	765	
		E2E Latency (ms)	97.11 [95.98, 98.25]	7.64	177	
		Power (wt)	55.78 [55.73, 55.83]	0.69	765	
	SHW-3	CPU (%)	4.28 [4.25, 4.32]	0.45	751	
		E2E Latency (ms)	101.93 [100.64, 103.21]	8.68	177	
		Power (wt)	54.5 [54.39, 54.61]	1.53	751	
	SHW-4	CPU (%)	4.93 [4.91, 4.95]	0.26	680	
		E2E Latency (ms)	104.85 [103.37, 106.33]	9.94	176	
		Power (wt)	54.01 [53.91, 54.12]	1.43	680	
	SHW-6	CPU (%)	4.25 [4.22, 4.29]	0.43	585	
		E2E Latency (ms)	102.89 [101.78, 104.0]	7.45	176	
		Power (wt)	51.95 [51.82, 52.08]	1.63	585	
	SHW-7	CPU (%)	4.54 [4.5, 4.59]	0.5	535	
		E2E Latency (ms)	103.43 [102.31, 104.54]	7.49	176	
		Power (wt)	53.2 [53.09, 53.31]	1.27	535	
	SHW-8	CPU (%)	2.08 [2.05, 2.1]	0.27	521	
		E2E Latency (ms)	106.68 [105.65, 107.7]	6.91	176	
		Power (wt)	140.59 [140.54, 140.64]	0.54	521	
	Italy	NFVI-I-1	CPU (u)	0.0 [0.0, 0.0]	0.0	930
			E2E Latency (ms)	98.62 [94.72, 102.52]	56.15	799
		NFVI-I-2	CPU (u)	2.0 [2.0, 2.0]	0.0	930
E2E Latency (ms)			92.09 [91.03, 93.16]	15.36	800	
NFVI-I-3		CPU (u)	1.0 [1.0, 1.0]	0.0	930	
		E2E Latency (ms)	93.56 [92.21, 94.92]	19.54	800	
NFVI-I-4		CPU (u)	0.0 [0.0, 0.0]	0.0	930	
		E2E Latency (ms)	88.85 [85.9, 91.79]	42.43	800	

FIGURE 12. E2E latency evolution for NFVI-I-3 and NFVI-I-4 with ZSM orchestrator decisions.

1) Experiment 1 - Cross-Domain Integrated Orchestration

To test the remote orchestration capabilities of the ZSM framework, the orchestrator is deployed at Campus Midde lheim (CMI) (University of Antwerp), a neutral third site separate from the management domains. This deliberate design choice serves to validate the management of geographically distributed testbeds, including the SHW in Belgium and NFVI-I in Italy, from a single point of control, which contrasts with the on-site deployment in the Romanian infrastructure. This setup enables the integration of analytics from heterogeneous NFVI-based management domains.

TABLE 7. Latency measurements for nodes NFVI-I-3, NFVI-I-4 and decisions from the ZSM orchestrator.

Record	Source	Node	E2E latency (ms)	Time (m:s:ms)
170189	metric	NFVI-I-3	93	02:11.336
170193	metric	NFVI-I-3	91	02:12.706
365081	decision	NFVI-I-3	93	02:13.338
365082	decision	NFVI-I-3	93	02:14.049
170197	metric	NFVI-I-3	134	02:14.106
365083	decision	NFVI-I-3	91	02:14.408
365084	decision	NFVI-I-3	91	02:14.794
365085	decision	NFVI-I-4	87	02:15.164
170202	metric	NFVI-I-4	88	02:15.544
365086	decision	NFVI-I-4	88	02:15.628
365087	decision	NFVI-I-4	88	02:16.158

TABLE 8. E2E Latency registered in NFVI-I during the cross-domain orchestration.

Orchestration Phase	Active Node	Mean E2E Latency (95% CI)	Peak Latency
Overload (Before)	NFVI-I-3	94.8 (90.5, 99.0) ms	134 ms
Stabilized (After)	NFVI-I-4	88.1 (87.3, 88.9) ms	92 ms
Mitigation Impact	36.6% Reduction (Best after peak: 85 ms Sustained: 88.1 ms)		

A total of eight Belgian edge nodes and four Italian nodes are orchestrated in parallel while the data is collected independently but simultaneously from these infrastructures and processed by the same decision engine. The ZSM orchestrator uses a technology-agnostic design to process KPIs in the original units reported by each NFVI, ensuring consistent decision-making across heterogeneous infrastructures. CPU KPI measurements in the Italian facilities are expressed in cores, while those in the Belgian SHW infrastructure are expressed in percentages, as seen in Figure 11 and Table 6.

In the Belgian and Italian testbeds, traffic is routed over 4G and the public internet, whereas in Romania, the ZSM framework is deployed on edge infrastructure within the 5G network. While the resulting average E2E latencies differ significantly (93 ms in Belgium, 102 ms in Italy, and 16 ms in Romania), the absolute values are not the primary focus of this experiment. Instead, the key objective is to evaluate the behavior of the ZSM framework and its responsiveness to latency variations. These diverse experimental setups demonstrate the flexibility of the ZSM framework to operate effectively even in demanding 5G environments.

The E2E latency values observed in this experiment are determined by the underlying network and compute infrastructure. The role of the ZSM framework is to minimize latency under given conditions by making high-quality orchestration decisions and integrating heterogeneous domains; however, the measured results ultimately depend on the network environment. Table 7 and Figure 12 provide a snapshot of the decision-making process, showing how the ZSM orchestrator adapts its deployment choice in response to latency variations, selecting NFVI-I-4 when it offers better performance.

TABLE 9. Latency measurements for nodes *ml-vm* and *ztm2-vm*.

Record	Node	E2E latency (ms)	Time (m:s.ms)
515128	ztm2-vm	20	23:09.776
515129	ztm2-vm	20	23:10.858
515130	ztm2-vm	17	23:10.984
515133	ztm2-vm	17	23:11.927
515136	ztm2-vm	17	23:13.023
515139	ztm2-vm	497	23:14.033
515140	ztm2-vm	497	23:14.148
515143	ztm2-vm	497	23:15.266
515146	ztm2-vm	497	23:16.368
515149	ztm2-vm	497	23:17.492
515152	ztm2-vm	497	23:18.604
515155	ml-vm	19	23:19.171
515158	ml-vm	19	23:20.191
515159	ml-vm	14	23:20.761

For a clearer analysis, the E2E latency records of nodes NFVI-I-3 and NFVI-I-4 are presented together with the decision value, which reflects the node offering the lowest latency. The system switches between these nodes only when the latency difference exceeds 30 ms. This value was chosen as a practical threshold, set near the observed standard deviation of latency for this connection (37.46 ms), to prevent unnecessary service migrations caused by routine network jitter, thus ensuring decision stability. In the observed behavior, NFVI-I-4 generally shows lower latency and is the selected environment until NFVI-I-3 reaches its maximum latency value of 134 ms at 14:02:14. At that point, the difference from NFVI-I-4 exceeds 30 ms (NFVI-I-4 at 86 ms), and the decision switches to NFVI-I-4. In this case, the system aims to optimize performance by prioritizing the lowest E2E latency while maintaining stability in the selection.

The orchestrator intervention triggered by the latency peak at 134 ms resulted in a substantial and sustained performance improvement. Immediately after migration, the minimum observed latency decreased to 85 ms, corresponding to a 36.6% reduction relative to the peak value as displayed in Table 8. Beyond this instantaneous relief, the statistical analysis confirms a clear stabilization of the system: the pre-migration phase, characterized by higher variability, was followed by a markedly stable operating regime with a reduced mean latency of 88.1 ms. These results indicate that the intervention not only mitigated the overload event but also restored stable service performance.

On the SHW testbed side, the ZSM orchestrator managed resource demands for vehicular applications across two distinct highway scenarios, each reflecting different vehicular traffic conditions and application needs. In Scenario-A (SHW-A), representing a high-density traffic section, the orchestrator prioritized low E2E latency to support critical safety applications, such as collision avoidance alerts. When E2E latency values across the Belgian edge nodes converged,

FIGURE 13. ZSM orchestrator decision traces from NFVI-R showing service migration actions triggered by E2E latency variations.

TABLE 10. E2E Latency registered in NFVI-R (Regular vs. Stress conditions).

KPI	Regular (pre-test)	Distribution (incl. stress)		
	Mean (95% CI)	Mean (95% CI)	5th Pctl	95th Pctl
E2E Latency (ms)	16.0 (15.6, 16.4)	61.3 (40.0, 82.6)	12	497
Spike Mitigation (%)	96.7% (95% bootstrap CI: 96.5%, 96.9%)			

power consumption became the deciding factor, favoring the node with lower power consumption. In Scenario-B (SHW-B), representing a section with light traffic, the priority shifted to power consumption first, as E2E latency is less critical. Across all SHW nodes, mean E2E latency remains tightly grouped between roughly 97 ms and 107 ms, with low variability ranging from 6.91 ms to 9.94 ms, reflecting stable performance under both prioritization modes.

The Belgium deployment has a higher mean E2E latency of 102.64 ms compared with 93.28 ms in the Italian deployment, but with far less variability: a standard deviation of 8.72 ms versus 37.46 ms. At the node level, the NFVI-I infrastructure shows uneven reliability.

2) Experiment 2 - On-Site Orchestration Validation

During the NFVI-R trials, E2E latency is monitored between a UE operating in a controlled laboratory environment and a video service instance distributed across three Virtual Machines (VMs) within the 5G NFVI edge infrastructure described in Section A. The UE streams live video from managed services, while E2E latency is measured by timestamping the transmission and reception of service requests across the live 5G infrastructure and continuously reporting the results to the ZSM orchestrator running on a Graphic Processing Unit (GPU)-enabled VM. Unlike the previous case, this experiment reflects the performance of a commercial-grade 5G system, thereby providing a realistic baseline for latency in operational mobile networks.

To evaluate the resilience of the ZSM framework in NFVI-R, concurrent users are introduced incrementally, with 500 new connections per second. Whenever latency exceeds the 100 ms threshold, which was previously defined as a practical performance target for this testbed to ensure reliable

FIGURE 14. Correlation heatmap of main KPIs (E2E latency, CPU load, and power consumption) from the SHW in Belgium.

communication for vehicular applications, the orchestrator dynamically migrates the service to a node with greater resource availability. This adaptive mechanism consistently maintains latency at approximately 16 ms, as seen in Table 10, even under stress conditions involving up to 1000 simultaneous users, thereby safeguarding the QoS required for real-time traffic monitoring and VRU protection.

Table 9 and Figure 13 present the trace records of the ZSM orchestrator decision process, showing that under high-load conditions, E2E latency on node `ztm2-vm` increases from 17.468 ms to 497.045 ms. Once the ZSM orchestrator detects this spike, it initiates a redeployment of the services to node `m1-vm`, which has greater resource availability, resulting in a rapid latency reduction to 18.878 ms while restoring the expected QoS. In the pre-test phase, as shown in Table 10, the system operates stably with a mean latency of 16.03 ms. Under stress traffic, the mean latency increases to 61.29 ms with a wide confidence interval, indicating high variability, and a 95th percentile of 497 ms. After the orchestrator intervention, a resampling analysis confirms a spike reduction of 96.7%, demonstrating effective performance recovery.

While temporary delays were detected during remote orchestration across the SHW and NFVI-I management domains, such additional lag does not occur in the NFVI-R 5G setup, as all ZSM components are co-located within the same geographical management domain. This result underscores the importance of collocating orchestration components with the managed infrastructure to minimize response times in latency-sensitive scenarios.

3) Experiment 3 - Energy-Aware ZSM for Sustainable Solutions

This experiment explores the potential of energy-aware solutions within the ZSM framework to optimize resource utilization while minimizing environmental impact. It focuses on the SHW testbed, since other facilities do not currently provide power consumption metrics. To evaluate

TABLE 11. Performance and power consumption KPIs measured for correlation analysis.

KPI	Regular (pre-test)		Dist. (incl. stress)	
	Avg Value	Std Value	5th Pctl	95th Pctl
CPU (%)	19	18	4	49
E2E latency (ms)	94	3	90	6643
Power (wt)	59	5	52	68

the correlation between workload intensity and energy usage, nodes are deliberately stressed to trigger consumption spikes, as seen in Table 11.

To measure E2E latency, an OBU sends REpresentational State Transfer (REST) calls to services hosted on the RSUs, and the round-trip time of these requests is recorded. The registered values are normalized to allow comparison, and the resulting KPIs for E2E latency, power consumption, and CPU utilization across multiple nodes show a clear interdependence between these metrics.

The strongest relationship is between E2E latency and power consumption: as E2E latency increases, power consumption rises in parallel, with both peaking in sync. For example, E2E latency rising from approximately 0.45 to 0.95 on the normalized scale corresponds to power increasing from approximately 0.50 to 0.92. Figure 14 illustrates this trend, where E2E latency and power points form a well-defined upward slope. To statistically validate this observation, we computed the Pearson correlation coefficient, which measures the linear relationship between variables. The analysis confirms a strong positive correlation between E2E latency and power consumption across all SHW nodes, with coefficients typically above 0.89. This high value indicates that higher E2E latency almost always coincides with increased power consumption, making these two KPIs suitable for joint optimization.

The correlation heatmaps in Figure 14, generated using this method, also show that the immediate correlation between CPU load and the other two metrics is weaker, with

TABLE 12. Summary of Lessons Learned from the implementation and validation of the ZSM Framework for cross-domain orchestration.

Lesson	Observation	Implication for Future Work	Relevance to ZSM for 6G Goals
Cross-domain orchestration requires balancing automation and latency overhead	Automation improved orchestration speed but added latency in geographically distributed setups (e.g., Belgium–Italy).	Explore distributed orchestrator placement near NFVI sites and optimize data pipelines.	Low-latency, scalable orchestration
Vendor lock-in and insufficient standardization hinder interoperability	Heterogeneous NFVI integration required domain-specific wrapper adaptations.	Promote open APIs and standardized telemetry to ease onboarding.	Interoperability, vendor agnosticism
Energy-aware orchestration enables sustainable operations	Energy–latency trade-offs validated in SHW testbed; framework prioritized savings under low load while keeping latency low.	Extend metrics to more NFVI and refine energy models for predictive orchestration.	Sustainability, resource efficiency
Closed-loop control enhances resilience and adaptability	Real-time monitoring and rule-based loops maintained service continuity under stress.	Integrate AI/ML for predictive maintenance and proactive orchestration.	Autonomous operation, resilience
ZSM operationalizes orchestration across the heterogeneous 6G compute continuum	Abstraction layer unified diverse administrative and technological domains (NFVI) into a single resource pool for consistent E2E management.	Test Domain Control Wrapper for zero-touch onboarding of new resource types and workloads, extending lifecycle management beyond edge/cloud domains.	Heterogeneity, E2E orchestration, scalability

coefficients generally between 0.15 and 0.27. This is because CPU reacts more slowly to changes in network conditions, often rising or falling only after E2E latency and power have already shifted. The delayed response keeps short-term correlation values low, even though the long-term trend aligns. While E2E latency and power can be managed as a tightly coupled pair, CPU performance requires separate monitoring and predictive orchestration that accounts for its slower dynamics.

These findings validate the role of multi-criteria decision-making in ZSM frameworks. By continuously monitoring correlated KPIs, the orchestrator can predict resource demands and balance performance with energy efficiency. Through proactive migration to more efficient nodes, dynamic scaling based on actual demand, and power-saving strategies during low-traffic periods, ZSM approaches can minimize environmental impact while maintaining strict QoS requirements.

VII. DISCUSSION AND LESSONS LEARNED

Building on these results, Table 12 summarizes the main insights from our experiments. The following discussion elaborates on these lessons, reflecting on challenges, limitations, and future work in cross-domain ZSM orchestration, with a focus on its relevance for 6G networks.

1) Balancing Automation with Latency Overhead

As highlighted in Table 12, effective cross-domain orchestration requires balancing the benefits of automation with inherent latency overhead. Our experiments revealed a clear

trade-off related to the geographical placement of the ZSM components. This was particularly evident in the communication between our central orchestrator in Belgium and the NFVI-I in Italy, where decision enactment took 1 to 1.8 seconds. In contrast, our experiment in the NFVI-R on a real 5G network demonstrated that co-locating the ZSM framework with the managed infrastructure is a critical lesson for B5G/6G. In that setup, decision changes were completed in just 350-500 ms, proving that a well-architected ZSM system can meet the stringent latency demands of future real-time applications. This suggests that for latency-critical 6G use cases, a distributed or hierarchical orchestration model, with decision-making functions placed closer to the edge, will be essential.

2) Overcoming Interoperability and Vendor Lock-in

Another key lesson is that overcoming vendor lock-in requires addressing the implementation gaps in existing standards. As established in Section IV, the ETSI ZSM framework provides the architectural blueprint but does not specify *how* to implement the data harmonization needed for seamless operation across different NFVIs. Our experiments confirmed this is a significant barrier, requiring considerable effort to adapt wrapper libraries for each new domain. The Domain Control Wrapper presented in this work offers a practical solution by providing a concrete data harmonization layer. However, our experience also underscores the critical need for wider adoption of standardized telemetry schemas and open APIs to reduce this onboarding complexity and truly achieve plug-and-play cross-domain orchestration.

In deployments with hundreds of nodes, the framework mitigates performance degradation through asynchronous data processing and lightweight decision logic, ensuring that decision latency does not grow with the number of monitored nodes. As studied in the literature [27], the orchestration load that directly impacts the duration of orchestration operations gets heavily affected by the number of orchestrated nodes. Thus, it is essential to pursue decentralized orchestration design. At larger scales, memory and processing resources must be managed carefully. Nodes can be grouped and assigned to separate managing domain deployments, allowing multiple orchestrators to operate within the same administrative domain while focusing on specific node groups. This distributed setup improves isolation, limits error propagation, and ensures that resources are provisioned where they are most needed.

3) Enabling Sustainable Operations Through Energy-Aware Orchestration

The experiments also highlighted the potential of ZSM to enable more sustainable network operations. The energy-latency trade-offs observed in the SHW testbed demonstrated that the framework can prioritize energy savings under low-load conditions. To build on this, future work must focus on extending energy consumption metrics to all participating NFVI. Furthermore, a holistic view of sustainability in 6G will require modeling the energy consumption not only of edge nodes but also of the transport network and higher-level cloud resources, since energy use in one part of the network can indirectly impact performance and costs in another. Integrating these broader energy models into the decision-making process is a key challenge for future ZSM research.

4) Enhancing Resilience With Closed-Loop Control

The experiments validated that closed-loop control is fundamental to enhancing service resilience and preventing local errors, such as infrastructure timeouts or telemetry spikes, from propagating into system-wide failures. Our framework addresses this by combining centralized anomaly detection (ZSM Monitoring) with distributed self-diagnosis (ZSM Deployers). ZSM Monitoring tracks performance metrics to identify service degradation, while distributed ZSM Control units perform local checks to verify action fulfillment. Crucially, the Domain Control Wrapper isolates managed-domain failures from the central orchestration logic, enabling the dynamic onboarding and offboarding of managed domains without disrupting orchestration operations and ensuring that local faults remain contained. The system also prevents queue overloading by halting subsequent actions while a task remains in the initialization phase, as described in Section IV-B.

While this rule based logic effectively ensures service continuity under stress conditions these decisions remain reactive. The next evolutionary step is to incorporate proactive control by leveraging AI/ML. For instance forecasting models could predict future QoS degradation allowing the system to act preemptively. Furthermore, advanced techniques like DRL could enable the orchestrator to learn complex adaptive policies for balancing conflicting objectives such as latency and energy consumption directly from environmental interactions. This transition from reactive rule enforcement to intelligent predictive control is a key direction for our future research.

5) Navigating the Heterogeneous Compute Continuum

Finally, the 6G vision is built on a “compute continuum”, a seamless fabric of computing resources stretching from end-user devices to the central cloud and designed to push user applications closer to the edge for improved performance. Our work validates the feasibility of such a continuum by orchestrating services across a heterogeneous mix of 4G, 5G, and public internet connections. This deployment serves as a functional microcosm of the 6G ecosystem, showing that unified orchestration is achievable across geographically distributed technological and administrative domains. It demonstrates that a ZSM approach, equipped with the right abstraction layers (e.g., the Domain Control Wrapper), can effectively manage network-intrinsic challenges such as varied performance characteristics and telemetry formats. Thus, the capacity to enforce unified, E2E orchestration across heterogeneous infrastructures is a critical technical requirement for implementing the 6G compute continuum.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a modular and technology-agnostic ZSM framework that unifies heterogeneous NFVI managed domains through an abstraction layer and a multi-criteria decision engine that evaluates latency, compute load, and energy consumption. Central to this solution is the capability to normalize diverse data types, enabling a unified analysis that streamlines orchestration with minimal human intervention. Experiments in real-world environments across three geographically distributed testbeds demonstrated that the system can autonomously mitigate severe latency spikes, improve performance under overload conditions, and remain stable despite heterogeneous telemetry formats and non-stationary network behavior. These results provide operational evidence that zero-touch orchestration across multiple domains is feasible and effective for emerging 6G compute-continuum environments.

Several open challenges remain. Meeting strict 6G latency targets will require more distributed or hierarchical orchestration approaches that reduce cross-site control delays. Broader standardization of telemetry models and interfaces is still needed to simplify the onboarding of new

managed domains and reduce reliance on custom integration logic. Future work will also explore predictive and proactive orchestration techniques, including forecasting and learning-based decision mechanisms, and extend energy-aware management by incorporating more complete E2E energy models. Addressing these challenges is essential to enable scalable and fully autonomous management across the 6G ecosystem.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Zaccarini *et al.*, “Voice: Value-of-information for compute continuum ecosystems,” in *2024 27th Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks (ICIN)*, 2024, pp. 73–80, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIN60470.2024.10494500>.
- [2] M. Liyanage *et al.*, “A Survey on Zero Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) for 5G and Beyond Networks,” *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 203, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2022.103362>.
- [3] W.-I. Press, *Network Softwarization View of 5G Networks*. Wiley-IEEE Press, 2018, pp. 499–518, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119333142.ch13>.
- [4] E. I. S. G. (ISG), “Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Reference Architecture,” ETSI GS ZSM 002 V1.1.1 (2019-08), 2019, online [Available]: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ZSM/001_099/002/01.01.01_60/gs_ZSM002v010101p.pdf, Date accessed: 2023-09-07.
- [5] E. T. S. Institute, *Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Means of Automation*. ETSI, 2020, online [Available]: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ZSM/001_099/005/01.01.01_60/gr_zsm005v010101p.pdf, Date accessed: 2024-08-07.
- [6] J. Niemöller *et al.*, “Autonomous Networks with MultiLayer Intent-based Operation,” *Ericsson Technology Review*, vol. 2023, no. 8, pp. 2–13, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.23919/ETR.2023.10313587>.
- [7] E. Coronado *et al.*, “Zero Touch Management: A Survey of Network Automation Solutions for 5G and 6G Networks,” *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 2535–2578, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2022.3212586>.
- [8] A. F. Ocampo and J. Santos, “Reinforcement Learning-Driven Service Placement in 6G Networks across the Compute Continuum,” in *2024 20th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, 2024, pp. 1–9, doi: <https://doi.org/10.23919/CNSM62983.2024.10814365>.
- [9] E. I. S. G. (ISG), “Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI); Transformer Architecture for Policy Translation,” ETSI GS ENI 030 V4.1.1 (2024-03), 2024, online [Available]: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ENI/001_099/030/04.01.01_60/gs_ENI030v040101p.pdf, Date accessed: 2025-06-26.
- [10] E. T. S. Institute, *Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Intent-driven autonomous networks; Generic aspects*. ETSI, 2023, online [Available]: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ZSM/001_099/011/01.01.01_60/gr_ZSM011v010101p.pdf, Date accessed: 2023-12-14.
- [11] H. Baba *et al.*, “End-to-End 5G Network Slice Resource Management and Orchestration Architecture,” in *2022 IEEE 8th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, 2022, pp. 269–271, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft54395.2022.9844088>.
- [12] J. Baranda *et al.*, “An AI/ML Proactive Network Service Relocation Approach for Multi-Admin Domain Scenarios,” in *NOMS 2024-2024 IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium*, 2024, pp. 1–3, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS59830.2024.10575207>.
- [13] S. L. Correa *et al.*, “Supporting MANOaaS and Heterogenous MANOaaS Deployment Within the Zero-Touch Network and Service Management Framework,” *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 4–11, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOMSTD.0001.2100088>.
- [14] E. T. S. Institute, *Zero-Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM); Terminology for Concepts in ZSM*. ETSI, 2023, online [Available]: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ZSM/001_099/007/02.01.01_60/gs_ZSM007v020101p.pdf, Date accessed: 2023-09-01.
- [15] 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), “5G; Service Requirements for Enhanced V2X Scenarios,” ETSI, Technical Specification TS 22.186, 2024, online [Available]: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/122100_122199/122186/18.00.01_60/ts_122186v180001p.pdf, Date accessed: 2025-02-12. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/122100_122199/122186/18.00.01_60/ts_122186v180001p.pdf
- [16] M. Yoon *et al.*, “An Efficient Network Operation Automation Scheme Using Network Status Information for Local 5G Networks,” in *2023 14th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)*, 2023, pp. 1447–1449, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTC58733.2023.10392675>.
- [17] J. Baranda *et al.*, “Multi-Administrative Domain Service Onboarding in a ZSM-Based Orchestration Architecture,” in *2023 20th Annual IEEE International Conference on Sensing, Communication, and Networking (SECON)*, 2023, pp. 366–368, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/SECON58729.2023.10287456>.
- [18] S. Barrachina-Muñoz *et al.*, “Empowering Beyond 5G Networks: An Experimental Assessment of Zero-Touch Management and Orchestration,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 182752–182762, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3510804>.
- [19] A. Tarrías *et al.*, “Toward Zero-Touch Cellular Networks via Next-Generation Crowdsourcing,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 167489–167497, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3489354>.
- [20] S. B. Chetty *et al.*, “Optimized Resource Allocation for Cloud-Native 6G Networks: Zero-Touch ML Models in Microservices-based VNF Deployments,” *IEEE Network*, pp. 1–1, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.2024.3486623>.
- [21] S. Kopp and R. M. Silveira, “Perspective Indicators for Service Orchestration in Zero-Touch Network and Service Management Context,” in *2024 7th International Conference on Information and Computer Technologies (ICICT)*, 2024, pp. 64–69, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICT62343.2024.00017>.
- [22] P. Szilágyi, “I2BN: Intelligent Intent Based Networks,” *Journal of ICT Standardization*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 159–200, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.13052/jicts2245-800X.926>.
- [23] N. Slamnik-Kriještorac *et al.*, “AI-Empowered Management and Orchestration of Vehicular Systems in the Beyond 5G Era,” *IEEE Network*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 305–313, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.008.2300024>.
- [24] T. Forum, “Autonomous Networks Technical Architecture v1.1.1 (IG1230),” Feb 2023, online [Available]: <https://www.tmforum.org/resources/introductory-guide/ig1230-autonomous-networks-technical-architecture-v1-1-1/>, Date accessed: 2025-02-28.
- [25] O. G. Lira *et al.*, “Large Language Models for Zero Touch Network Configuration Management,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, pp. 1–8, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.001.2400368>.
- [26] B.-S. Kim *et al.*, “A survey on analytical models for dynamic resource management in wireless body area networks,” *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 135, p. 102936, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2022.102936>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1570870522001196>
- [27] N. Slamnik-Kriještorac *et al.*, “Collaborative orchestration of multi-domain edges from a connected, cooperative and automated mobility (ccam) perspective,” *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2001–2020, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMC.2021.3118058>.